

A floating blue ring flew into the candle flame

Introduction

This post describes a phenomenon I witnessed. I do not have an explanation, but recording and sharing it with the scientific community is essential. Given my current state of knowledge, my personal guess is that it could be a ring of self-flying plasma. But I'm not knowledgeable in this field, so I'm just leaving this entry here and trying to outline some of the circumstances.

Site description

It happened in the 1990s in an apartment in Prague 5, the Czech Republic. The apartment was located on the second floor of a house from the end of the 19th century, so it was probably bricked and plastered. The windows were wooden with glass panes. There was no storm; it did not rain.

Two people were sitting in the room where the incident happened, and a candle was burning on the table. In addition, there was a Mora brand gas furnace, probably type PO 370. This gas furnace burned a constant blue flame. These heat exchanger furnaces used to be grounded. Also in the room was probably a Merkur television from the Czechoslovak manufacturer Tesla, a computer screen, a computer and an input device, and an old Tesla tape player. Then, the metallic shower box and wooden furniture with books and clothes. One window, two wooden doors, and an open entrance to the kitchen. The ceiling was about 3 meters from the vinyl floor.

Description of the event

I was sitting at the table beside me with a burning candle. Suddenly, I noticed a wavy ring of blue color in front of my eyes, similar in color to a flame of fire. This ring flew about from the heat exchanger and the window and did not have a constant circular shape, but it undulated and variously shriveled and stretched like it was floating in the air. When it approached the flame of the candle, it was as if the flame pulled it because the ring partially flew around the flame and then flew into it. The candle sputtered and went out. The ring disappeared.